

Explicating the Nuances of Segregation in J.M. Coetzee's *Waiting for the Barbarians*

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The term Segregation can mean the act of isolating, the fact or condition of being isolated or standing alone, separated from other things or persons, solitariness, the obtaining of a chemical element or compound as a separate substance, separation of a person or thing from its normal environment a particular wish or thought loses emotional significance by being isolated from its normal context. This last meaning relates directly to the Apartheid politics of South Africa. Isolation, then, also comes across as a negative term, but the isolation could be both voluntary or involuntarily. Isolation appears to happen on a physical as well as a psychological level.

Coetzee’s *Waiting for the Barbarians* (1980) was the novel that brought him international acclaim. Its title is taken from the 1904 poem *Waiting for the Barbarians* by Costantine Cavafy. The Empire in both the novel and the poem is in a sense dependent upon an Other, a barbarian enemy to strengthen the national feeling of the state . The novel was more often than not read in an unspecified time and place as an allegory with a strong focus on the South African security police and how the language of the novel reflects the language of the oppression of the apartheid regime. In dealing with torture problems, the novel was scrutinized on its publishing by the censors, but avoided being partially banned owing to the apparent distance from South Africa of the setting.

Saunders suggestions as a manner of entering the text and commenting on some of the novels key problems. She gives the foreign interesting discussion; the Other. According to Saunders, the foreigner is one who speaks a different language. In this way, when people have different languages, they are classified as foreign, or isolated from each other. The Magistrate desperate in *Waiting for the Barbarians* when the prisoners of Colonel Joll are not the barbarians The Other is obviously not just one type of Other, but a diversity of Others. Colonel Joll, unaware of the frontier settlement’s geopolitical dynamics, sees only in black and white: prisoners are prisoners. This makes him unable to tell the foreigners difference. Therefore, understanding of what distinguishes barbarians from fishermen is heavily linked to authority, but it also depends on space.

Flavours of Literature

The theme of segregation is the notion of foreignness. Foreignness is made visible by acts of invasion because it imposes a concept of distinction, separating or isolating from each other the Suppressor and the Suppressed. However, the city itself, being a colony, is alien to the land in many ways, but it has become familiar through invasion. Thus the Magistrate sees himself as an alien in the land as well as at home in it. His own understanding of the location is superior after Joll's arrival, and Joll's ignorance of boundary customs shows him as an alien, but a right-wing stranger. Secondly, Saunders argument on context control can be seen by the reader. This context control is precisely what allows Joll and his troops from distant capital to be regarded as insiders, while the barbarians who in fact are more strongly linked to the border settlement in both geographical and social terms are regarded as outsiders, as enemies. Joll, who in his deeds represents colonial authority and oppression, writes the barbarians he brings back to city as Other, or enemy.

For instance, each finds that they are strangers in the land when the magistrate and Joll leave city on their distinct missions deeper into the borderland. Predicting his own and Joll's borderland expeditions, they both later discover that without their permission they can get nowhere close the true barbarians. Moreover, when the magistrate returns the girl to her people, the language they speak is not understood and is isolated from understanding. Admitting that he cannot make out a word, he regrets not having her teach her tongue to him. Nevertheless, he must in a sense invade her and force her to talk for him to enter her language.

Coetzee through his imagination, has the capacity to cross these limits. On the other hand, the magistrate can't imagine the girl without the marks, or the depth of Joll's abuse of her, even with the noticeable indications of torture on the girl's body. Not until he has entered the realm of torture himself, not as an onlooker, but as a victim, can he begin to understand the suffering and silence of the girl and become truly identified. The space visualizes a boundary between invasion and isolation. The victim is held in solitary confinement inside. Joll or Mandel enter the space, invading the victim's space as well as mind and body. Excluded, as the novelist does, the magistrate is isolated outside the room and tries to invade the space.

Coetzee frequently took the novels through the exclusion itself is what spurs the questioning of what has happened in the room by the magistrate. His own eyes are prevented from seeing, his ears do not hear the screaming which people afterwards claim to have heard from the granary, so he questions his guards and the boy who was interrogated, trying to read the signs on his body. As demonstrated in his connection with the barbarian girl, the confined space as the environment of interrogation is continued by the Magistrate himself. In a way, he stages his own torture room re-enactment. His own chambers become the barbarian girls isolated prison. Yet the body of the barbarian girl comes to represent in its own right a closed room, one that the magistrate wants to invade, but finds no way to enter. Unable to look into her, she continues as a reminder of her inability and impotence to discover what moves her.

Therefore, this revelation of Segregation and struggles of isolation in terms of a race, class, and gender issues in Coetzee's novel like *Waiting for the Barbarians*, end in confession .

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